

A Perspective on Additive Manufacturing for BASOSH (Bodycentric Antenna Systems for Occupational Safety and Health)

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1-PAGE EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing can potentially allow for the creation of personalized BASOSH (bodycentric antenna systems applied to occupational safety and health). In this brief perspective, we define the BASOSH, describe current uses of additive manufacturing for OSH (occupational safety and health), and identify opportunities and challenges of additively manufactured BASOSH.

A. BASOSH Definition

Based on the definition introduced in [1], body-centric antenna systems (BAS) are wireless networked systems designed to operate in close proximity to, on, or within the human body. BAS are conceptualized as interconnected systems in which the human body itself becomes an integral part of the transmission medium. Several studies have already explored the application of BAS in occupational safety scenarios [2, 3], but a formal systematization of these approaches into a dedicated category has not been established before, even though they are characterized by unique challenges as hereafter reported.

B. BASOSH Applications

BASOSH applications reported by the literature include smart personal protective equipment (PPE) ensuring correct usage and preserved functionalities, as well as body-worn sensors for detecting noxious substances (e.g., toxins and nanomaterials) and environmental factors such as noise, microclimate, radiation, and vibrations. BASOSH also supports telemonitoring, potentially through implanted devices and real-time data transmission, enabling the identification and quantification of relevant biomarkers. Additional applications involve on-body data gathering for detecting unknown or synergistic risks, worker localization, access control, and support for search and rescue operations. Wireless power transfer can be exploited to sustain body-centric sensors and cyber-prostheses, while optimized off-body radio links improve communication reliability through tailored propagation models. Further benefits include enhanced work efficiency, acquisition of otherwise inaccessible environmental information (e.g., R-FAD for sensorial ultrability [2]), ergonomic assessment in workplaces, automated notification of accidents and near-misses, environmental scanning for risk identification, and direct communication of safety measures to workers.

C. Additive Manufacturing Research for OSH

Recent literature has begun to explore the use of additive manufacturing in OSH-related applications [4]. Reported developments include personalized prosthetics tailored to individual workers, allowing the full social reintegration of the individual. Another application regards micro-scale

Fig. 1 Concept of an additively manufactured cyber-prosthetic BASOSH.

scaffolds for in vitro testing of biological risks. Additive manufacturing has also enabled the production of customized PPE, along with engineered microstructures such as biocidal surfaces for contamination control. Personalized materials and reconfigurable structures can allow adaptive and application-specific solutions.

D. Additive Manufacturing in BASOSH: Challenges and Opportunities

Several challenges remain, including biocompatibility for implanted devices, structural durability in harsh environments, the need for multiple 3D-printing techniques to achieve flexibility and functional integration, resolution limitations, potential retention of harmful substances, and performance conflicts such as combining metallic components for osteointegration with conductive elements for wireless communication (Fig. 1). Additionally, 3D-printed antennas may experience reduced radiation efficiency in proximity to the human body, necessitating system-level co-design approaches. Nevertheless, additive manufacturing is crucial for realizing advanced, personalized BASOSH and for collecting data to improve occupational safety and rehabilitation strategies. By bridging additive manufacturing with BASOSH, we can push forward the new paradigm of *personalized OSH*, tailored on the needs of the specific worker.

References

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